

STATIC AND SEISMIC EFFECT OF CONSTRUCTING A NEW TUNNEL VERTICALLY ABOVE AN EXISTING TUNNEL: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

S.T.Amin¹, S.M.Abbas² and A.Usmani³

¹Research Scholar, Corresponding Author, Department of Civil Engineering,
JMI, New Delhi

² Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, JMI, New Delhi

³ DGM, ETDD, EIL, New Delhi
tabassumamin56@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The necessity for underground tunnels is of paramount importance in today's advancing world of development and transportation. Construction of twin tunnels have gained momentum due to their optimal utilization of underground space and enhanced structural stability. Particularly in earthquake prone regions, the seismic vulnerability of such subterranean structures is a significant issue. This research studies the impact of constructing a new tunnel vertically above an existing one, by increasing the vertical spacing under both static and seismic conditions. A 2D plane strain model is designed using Mohr-Coulomb criteria in Midas GTS NX software. The seismic simulation is performed using the Loma Preita earthquake in the horizontal direction. For this study, SeismoMatch generates response spectra-compatible time history data for Delhi soil. The responses generated within the existing tunnel are compared before and after the construction of the new tunnel, in the form of lining forces and ground settlement contours for static and seismic cases. The findings indicate that due to construction of a new tunnel, lining forces decrease in the existing tunnel. In static analysis, forces such as axial force, bending moment and shear force however increase with greater spacing. Similar trend is observed in seismic analysis, where these forces are greater in single tunnel than in twin tunnel. This can be attributed to the vertical position and spacing of the new tunnel which aids in load sharing mechanism between the two tunnels. This phenomenon plays a pivotal role in the static and dynamic stability of the twin tunnel system.

KEYWORDS

Twin Tunnels, Alluvial Silts, Static & Seismic Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Proper utilization of underground space is highly essential to accommodate the increase in demand of transportation, storage or utility requirements, especially in populated urban areas. Due to the same, twin tunnelling or multiple tunnelling has gained momentum in the world of modern transportation and communication. However, there is a dire need of research to study the structural vulnerability of these underground structures in seismically active regions. The selection of authentic ground motion holds pivotal importance in ensuring the precision of seismic analysis conducted on underground tunnels. In cases where seismic data is unavailable for a particular location, seismic records obtained from a comparable site can be employed for analytical purposes. Nonetheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that such an approach might lead to an overestimation of the resultant response [1].

For accurate analysis, the actual earthquake time history must be converted into response spectra time history. The impact of constructing a second tunnel on the response of the existing

tunnel can help engineers understand the variation of vertical stresses and forces in RC liners with different pillar widths. This can help guide the selection of appropriate design parameters to ensure tunnel safety and stability [2]. Also, the tunnel's bearing capacity decreases sharply during strong earthquakes, and the lining is destroyed, resulting in a large residual internal force. The interaction of parallel tunnels influences the internal force distribution and the magnitude of adjacent surface acceleration. When parallel tunnels are present, the ground acceleration is amplified, resulting in a doubled peak increment of ground acceleration when compared to the single tunnel case [3]. The presence of underground structures, such as tunnels and stations, can have a significant impact on the soil's dynamic response.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Numerical Modelling

A 2D plane strain soil model is constructed with the help of Midas GTS NX (using Finite Element Modelling) software. The dimensions of the 2D model are 180 X 100m as shown below in Figure 1. The soil model consists of seven different layers with variation in modulus of elasticity with depth as shown in Table 1 to resemble realistic ground conditions which have been modified from [1]. Elasto-plastic property of Mohr-Coulomb soil condition is considered for all the layers of soil model. The dimensions of the tunnel are chosen from [1]. The tunnel has a diameter (D) of 6.26m, as mentioned in Table 2. The tunnel is located at a depth of 46.87m below the ground surface. 1D beam elements are chosen to simulate tunnel lining, which exhibits only elastic property. No slip condition (perfect bond) is considered between the tunnel lining and the surrounding soil. Ground water table is not considered. Damping of 10% and 5% are assigned to each layer of soil and tunnel lining respectively. The important properties of the tunnel lining adopted from [1] and [2] are thereby mentioned in Table 3. A new tunnel of same diameter is considered in the vertical twin tunnel arrangement as illustrated in Figure 1. Here, the distance of the new tunnel is varied at 1.5D, 2D, 2.5D, 3D and 3.5D from the centre of the existing tunnel. (D= Diameter of the existing tunnel).

After assigning the soil and tunnel properties, the model comprising of single tunnel and twin tunnel are finely meshed using 4-noded quadrilateral elements up to a maximum size of 1m. A high quality mesh should be created to acquire the required accuracy, convergence, reduce the time and thereby fasten the process of simulation. The tunnels are meshed initially followed by the multiple soil layers. The mesh of tunnel lining is extracted from the excavation mesh.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of soil-tunnel model

2.2. Seismic Input

Loma Preita earthquake (1989) is selected for the seismic analysis. Since Delhi falls in seismic zone IV [4], it is important to produce an artificial earthquake which is compatible for Delhi soils (alluvial silts) to generate realistic ground responses. Hence, with the help of SeismoMatch software response spectra compatible time history data is generated using Loma Preita earthquake data as shown in Figure 2. The original Loma Preita earthquake had a PGA of 0.367g whereas the artificial earthquake has a PGA of 0.125g. This artificially generated time history data has a total time period of 40sec. The earthquake is applied horizontally to the soil-tunnel model for a time period of 12 sec to expedite the computational process of the analysis as it was the dominant time period of the earthquake.

Figure 2. Loma Preita Earthquake Time History Data

Table 1. Variation of Elastic Modulii with depth

Depth (m)	Thickness (m)	Elastic Modulus (kPa)
0-10	10	7500
10-20	10	15000
20-35	15	30000
35-50	15	40000
50-60	10	50000
60-80	20	65000
80-100	20	80000

Table 2. Tunnel lining properties

Properties	Values
Diameter of both tunnels, D	6.26m
Overburden depth, H	46.87m
Thickness of RC liners	0.28m
S_D (Centre to centre distance/Diameter of the tunnel)	1.5 to 3.5
Elastic modulus of RC liners, E_C	3.16×10^7 kPa
Poisson's ratio of concrete	0.15

Table 3. Mechanical properties of soil

Properties	Values
Unit weight, γ_{bulk}	18 kN/m^3
Saturated unit weight, γ_{sat}	20 kN/m^3
Cohesion, c	0
Friction angle, Φ	35°
Dilatancy angle, Ψ	5°
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.25

2.3. Analysis Procedure

For static analysis, all the nodes of the vertical boundaries are hinged in x-direction to allow free movement in the y-direction. The bottom boundary is fixed in all directions to simulate bottom rock condition. This is followed by Eigen value analysis, where ground surface springs are applied to the soil model only. Now in case of seismic analysis, absorbent boundaries are applied at vertical sides to replicate free field ground conditions. Various stages involved in the complete analysis are mentioned below:-

Stage1: To generate initial stresses, at-rest earth pressure coefficient, “ K_0 condition” is considered by activating all the soil layers only. The soil excavation and lining are not activated in this stage.

Stage2: Soil in the first tunnel is removed. Volume contraction of 3% is applied to simulate percentage of ground loss volume during excavation. Here, the tunnel lining is simultaneously installed to avoid collapse of the tunnel cavity.

Stage3: Similar steps as mentioned in *Stage 2* are repeated for the new tunnel at a particular distance.

Stage4: Static analysis is carried out for the whole system and the resulting stresses get stored as the initial stress condition prior to the occurrence of earthquake.

Stage5: Modal analysis is performed to generate dominant modes of frequencies, which are used to calculate mass and stiffness proportional coefficients, α and β respectively.

Stage6: Non-linear time history analysis is finally performed by incorporating α and β from *Stage5* and applying the artificially generated earthquake in the positive x-direction to the soil-tunnel model.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static and seismic impact produced on the existing tunnel lining before and after construction of the new tunnel are presented in the form of tunnel lining forces such as axial force, bending moment, shear force and ground displacement of the surrounding soil medium.

3.1. Static Analysis

The process of construction of a new tunnel involves the removal of soil from the path of the tunnel. This removal of soil followed by installation of tunnel lining changes the entire load distribution mechanism of the surrounding soil. This leads to redistribution of stresses in the soil medium which get stored as initial stresses before the excavation of new tunnel. So, the aim of this study is to understand the effect of construction of this new tunnel on the existing tunnel lining and the surrounding soil medium. Figure 3(a) shows the variation of axial force with respect to S_D in the existing tunnel lining, where S_D is the ratio of centre-to-centre distance between the tunnels and the diameter of the tunnel (D).

The variation of bending moment and shear force in the existing tunnel lining also show a similar pattern as shown in Figure 3(b) and 3(c). Due to excavation and construction of a new tunnel, the axial force, bending moment and shear force decrease in the existing tunnel. This decrease in the lining forces increases with increase in S_D . This may be due to the fact that when a new tunnel is constructed above an existing tunnel, some of the vertical loads are now carried by the new tunnel. This leads to reduced vertical load on the existing tunnel and hence, the existing tunnel lining generates lesser forces as compared to a single tunnel. However, on increasing the distance between the two tunnels, the soil bridge between the two tunnels elongates in distance. This generates greater vertical load from the soil on the existing tunnel and hence, the lining forces consecutively increase. This can be understood from the ground settlement contours as shown in Figure 4. When the new tunnel is at the furthest from the

existing tunnel as seen in Figure 4(c)), the disturbance of the soil around the existing tunnel is way more than as compared to Figure 4(b) when the new tunnel is nearest to the existing tunnel.

3(a)

3(b)

3(c)

Figure 3. Variation of (a) axial force (b) bending moment (c) shear force in the existing tunnel after excavation of new tunnel.

4(a)

4(b)

4(c)

Figure 4. Variation of ground settlement contours in (a) single tunnel and new tunnel at (b) 1.5D (c) 3.5D

3.2. Seismic Analysis

The single and the twin tunnel models are further seismically analyzed by non-linear time history analysis using Loma Preita earthquake. The lining forces and ground settlement contours are compared. The variation of axial force in the single tunnel and twin tunnel are shown in Figure 5(a). In case of twin tunnel, it is observed to be less than that as in the existing tunnel and does not show much variation as S_D increases. Similar pattern is observed in case of bending moment and shear force as seen in Figure 5(b) and 5(c). In case of single tunnel system, the existing tunnel solely carries the seismic load in contrast to a twin tunnel system where the load gets shared between the tunnels. This helps in generating lower bending moment in the twin tunnel system. Hence, it can be correctly stated that a twin tunnel system is more seismically stable than a single tunnel.

Contrary to static analysis, the axial force, bending moment and shear force in the existing tunnel are almost constant as S_D increases. This may be attributed to the vertical alignment of the twin tunnels as the overburden stress from the soil between the two tunnels does not suffer much alteration due to the horizontally applied earthquake. Hence, it can be concluded that in presence of a horizontal earthquake, the vertical twin tunnels behave independently irrespective of the distance between them. This can also be understood from the ground settlement contours as shown in Figure 6, where the settlement troughs around the existing tunnel do not undergo much variation as the new tunnel is positioned from 1.5D to 3.5D.

5(a)

5(b)

5(c)

Figure 5. Variation of (a) Axial Force (b) Bending Moment (c) Shear Force in the existing tunnel after the earthquake.

Figure 6. Variation of ground settlement contours in (a) Single tunnel and new tunnel at (b) 1.5D (c) 3.5D after the earthquake

From static analysis, it is observed that after a distance of 2.5D, the difference in variation of all the parameters between the existing tunnel and twin tunnel gradually decrease. Same is observed in case of seismic analysis. It is essential to find a feasible distance between the two tunnels to ensure static and dynamic stability. Hence, as per the present study, an ideal distance of 2.5D-3D between the existing tunnel and a new tunnel will be optimum to be both statically and seismically safe. Here, the governing factor in deciding the distance is actually derived from the static analysis.

4. LIMITATIONS

The research carried out in this paper is a preliminary study which compares and analyses the static and seismic behaviour of a single and a twin tunnel system in 2D plane strain condition. The ground water table condition is not considered in the analysis. Also, partial slip condition or full slip condition is ignored. Earthquake is applied only in horizontal direction whereas earthquake in y or z-direction can also create serious impact on an underground structure. Hence, a complete 3D analysis considering full slip condition and groundwater table should also be carried out for better evaluation of static and seismic forces in the tunnels.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Tunnels are important underground structures which require comprehensive study, especially in an earthquake-prone zone to avoid any possible damage due to a seismic event. Hence, in this paper, static and seismic analyses are performed on a single and a twin tunnel system. The impact is observed on the existing tunnel due to a new tunnel at different vertical distances.

Artificially generated response spectra compatible Loma Preita earthquake data is used in the non-linear time history analysis. The interaction effect is studied in the form of parameters such as lining forces and ground settlement contours. Based on the above study, it can be concluded that:

Static analysis:

- After construction of a new tunnel, lining forces of the existing tunnel such as axial force, bending moment and shear force decrease as compared to a single tunnel. This is due to the sharing of overburden load between the two tunnels.
- Lining forces of the existing tunnel tend to increase on increasing the distance between the tunnels. This results from gradual increment of overburden stress from the increasing soil bridge between the tunnels.

Seismic analysis:

- Axial force, bending moment and shear force of the existing tunnel are greater in case of single tunnel than in twin tunnel system. This may be due to indifference in the overburden stress from the horizontally applied earthquake.
- Also, the lining forces tend to remain constant on increasing the distance between the two tunnels. Hence, the observed results in the existing tunnel are independent of the vertical positioning of the twin tunnels in case of earthquake.

Based on this research, an optimum distance of 2.5D-3D will be ideal for construction of a new tunnel vertically above to counter both static and seismic loads safely.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my sincere appreciation for the invaluable support that Midas GTS NX has provided me, enabling me to access the software and conduct my research effectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Singh, M. N. Viladkar, and N. K. Samadhiya, "Seismic response of metro underground tunnels," *Int. J. Geotech. Eng.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 175–185, 2017, doi: 10.1080/19386362.2016.1201881.
- [2] M. Singh, M. N. Viladkar, and N. K. Samadhiya, "Static and seismic analysis of twin metro underground tunnels," *Lect. Notes Civ. Eng.*, vol. 86, pp. 241–257, 2021, doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-6233-4_17.
- [3] S. Li, Y. Chen, L. Huang, and E. Guo, "Study on Response and Influencing Factors of Shield Single/Twin Tunnel under Seismic Loading using FLAC 3D," *Shock Vib.*, vol. 2022, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/2224198.
- [4] IS-1893-Part-1, "Criteria for Earthquake Resistant Design of Structures - General Provisions and Buildings Part-1," *Bur. Indian Stand. New Delhi*, vol. Part 1, no. 1, pp. 1–39, 2002.

Authors

Corresponding author- Sumeet Tabassum Amin

Short Biography

Sumeet Tabassum Amin is a Research Scholar in the Department of Civil Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi. She graduated in Civil Engineering (2015) and completed her Masters in Earthquake Engineering (2018) from the same institute. She is currently carrying out her PhD research in the field of seismic analysis of underground twin tunnels in Delhi soils.

